

Bridging the Digital Divide: The Role of Open Source Software in Strengthening Community ISPs

OFA Symposium 2025 - Presentation of Ongoing Research
Track #1: Economic Impact of Open

October, 2025

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*****This paper constitutes a draft summary of the report currently being developed by Connect Humanity within the framework of the 4th cohort of the Digital Infrastructure Investment Fund (DIIF) program*****

1. Introduction

By 2023, internet access had expanded to 86% of Brazilian households. Yet, despite this ostensibly high level of penetration, only 22% of the population could be said to possess *meaningful connectivity*—defined as access with adequate data allowances, sufficient speed, and appropriate devices (ICT Households 2024, Núcleo de Informação e Coordenação do Ponto BR, 2024). The evident gap in Internet access and quality of access is strongly marked by economic class, the difference between urban and rural areas, race, and is also unequal across the five major Brazilian regions (north, northeast, midwest, southeast, and south).

Small ISPs, of which there are more than 11,000 in Brazil (Núcleo de Informação e Coordenação do Ponto BR, 2022), play an important role in filling this connectivity gap. A considerable portion of them use Open Source Software (OSS) to reduce network deployment and maintenance costs, but they face significant challenges, including differences in technical knowledge, limited technical support, and issues with interface usability. This study will gather empirical data on the adoption of OSS by small providers, as well as assess these barriers and opportunities, providing knowledge to inform policymakers, funders, and community connectivity initiatives.

This research is justified by the extensive body of literature in recent years that consistently links internet access to economic development and the reduction of social inequalities (Van Dijk, 2012; Wessels, 2013; Whitacre, Gallardo & Strover, 2014; Senne, 2022). Further, Internet access is included as a goal of the United Nations' Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), with Goal 9(c) explicitly including universal access at affordable prices as one of its objectives: "significantly increase access to information and communication technologies and strive to provide universal and affordable access to the internet in least developed countries by 2020" (UN, 2015). Moreover, the research is also justified by the fact that, to the best of our knowledge, there is no specific systematized empirical data on the use of OSS by small ISPs in Brazil, nor are there any academic articles on other countries addressing the issue.

Track #1 of the OFA Symposium in Rio, focused on the "Economic Impact of Open" is aligned with this report as understanding the adoption of open technologies by ISPs is directly related to shaping competitive and resilient markets, as well as developing rural and remote parts of emerging economies such as the Brazilian one.

2. Research Objectives

The primary objectives of this research are twofold: first, to identify and analyze the patterns of Open Source Software (OSS) adoption among small Internet service providers (ISPs); and second, to assess the extent to which greater reliance on OSS can enhance both the sustainability and the accessibility of the services offered by these providers.

To achieve these objectives, the study will map the current use of OSS among small ISPs, examining not only the degree of adoption but also the key factors that motivate or hinder its use. It will further investigate providers' perceptions and demands with respect to costs, usability, the lack of technical training, and the limited availability of specialized support.

Scholars are increasingly seeking to quantify the societal and economic contribution of open-source software (OSS) (Blind, K., & Schubert, 2024, Hoffmann, Nagle and Zhou, 2024). Hoffmann, Nagle, and Zhou (2024) estimate that the supply-side contribution of widely adopted OSS amounts to approximately USD 4.15 billion, while its demand-side value reaches an estimated USD 8.8 trillion. They further suggest that, in the absence of OSS, firms would incur software expenditures roughly 3.5 times higher than current levels.

However, the relevance of OSS extends beyond the mere reduction of costs. Its adoption contributes to the creation of open, collaborative ecosystems of exchange and development, while also lowering the temporal costs associated with selecting and adapting software and training personnel. In this sense, the notion of 'cost' is understood in a broader perspective, encompassing not only financial outlays but also operational efficiency and organizational learning.

3. Data on Internet access and Internet Service Providers in Brazil

In 2023, internet penetration in Brazil reached 86% of households. However, despite this seemingly high rate, only 22% of the population enjoys what can be considered "meaningful connectivity"¹, that is, access characterized by adequate data allowances,

¹ The concept of "meaningful connectivity" was first discussed in the Web Foundation's "Alliance for Affordable Internet (A4AI)". It refers not only to the presence or absence of connectivity, but also to the amount of data available, whether it allows unlimited data use or not, the connection speed, and the type of device used to connect, which are determining factors for the greater or lesser quality and ability of the user to enjoy the benefits of the Internet.

sufficient speed, and the use of appropriate devices (ICT - Households 2024 - Núcleo de Informação e Coordenação do Ponto BR, 2024). A total of 29 million Brazilians are not internet users, of which 24 million live in urban areas, 22 million have only elementary school education, 17 million identify as black or brown, and 16 million belong to classes D and E².

Connectivity in places of lesser economic interest to large companies is provided by small and medium-sized ISPs. Graph 1 below shows that the more than 11,000 internet service providers analyzed in the 2022 ICT Providers Survey account for 38.2% of the fixed broadband market, while 12 other large companies account for the remaining 61.8%.

Graph 1 - Market share of companies in the Fixed Broadband market in Brazil - 2025

Source: ANATEL, 2025.

Internet usage surveys conducted by Cetic.br and monthly usage reports from the Brazilian regulator (ANATEL) both point to internet access increasingly being carried out directly through the cellular telephone network and mainly through mobile devices, which on the one hand increases the population's overall digital inclusion, and on the other hand poses problems in terms of meaningful connectivity and the ability of these users to use the internet creatively and freely.

The inequality of access to the Internet in Brazil becomes quite clear: the Internet is present in 98% of class A households, but in only 67% of class D and E households.

² The classification used by the Cetic.br survey uses economic class as an approximation of social class. This economic classification is based on the Brazilian Economic Classification Criteria (CCEB) defined by the Brazilian Association of Research Companies (Abep).

Regarding forms of internet access in Brazil, cell phones remain the main device used, with 99% of users using this medium, and 30% of users accessing the internet only via cell phone, a figure that rises to 50% in classes D and E. ([Nic.br](#), 2023).

The latest published survey is "TIC Provedores 2022" ([Nic.br](#), 2023), for which 2,008 internet service providers were interviewed, and which found that in 2022 there were 11,630 internet service providers in Brazil (a decrease from 12,826 in 2020). Of these providers, 46% were micro-enterprises in 2022 (a reduction from the total of 56% of micro-enterprises in 2020) ([Nic.br](#), 2023).

According to the Cetic.br survey, of these 11,630 companies, 60% offered internet access through their own infrastructure, and 37% through their own and third-party infrastructure. Among the technologies used, fiber optics was the most prevalent, being offered to customers by 95% of providers, followed by 60% use of "Wireless access via free frequency" (Wi-Fi); "Access via UTP cable (Ethernet)," with 35%; "Wireless access via licensed frequency," 27%; access via cable modem, 18%; access via 3G or 4G modem, 10%; and "Access via ADSL," also with 10% of provider companies using this technology. Regarding the territory covered by providers, among companies with up to 9 employees, 60% operated in only one municipality, 35% in two to five municipalities, and 3% in six to ten municipalities.

With respect to connection costs and prices charged by ISPs in Brazil, data from the TIC Domicílios 2023 survey indicate that among households with internet access, the majority (55%) spend between R\$51 and R\$100 per month (approximately USD 10–20), followed by 23% who spend between R\$101 and R\$150 (USD 20–30). Meanwhile, 11% report monthly expenditures of up to R\$50 (up to USD 10), and only 4% spend more than R\$150 (USD 30). A pronounced socioeconomic disparity is also evident: the highest expenditure category, above R\$150 per month (over USD 30), is most common among households in class A (25%), while in all other socioeconomic classes this proportion does not exceed 5% (TIC Domicílios, 2023).

The value of access to the Internet itself tells us little, but it takes on profound meaning when cross-referenced with the monthly income of families:

Among households with Internet access that have no income or whose family income is up to three minimum wages, 87% committed more than 2% of the family income to the connection, a proportion that was 41% for those with a family income between three and five minimum wages and close to 0% among those with a family income higher than five minimum wages. The proportion of households that committed more than 2% of the family income to the Internet

connection was also higher in the North (73%) and Northeast (73%) regions compared to the South region (57%).(TIC Domicílios, 2023).

With regard to the costs associated with operating an ISP in Brazil, and the extent to which these can be reduced through the adoption Open Source Software (OSS), the absence of systematic data on the interface between ISPs and OSS complicates any initial estimation. Nevertheless, as discussed above, the relevance of OSS extends beyond the mere reduction of costs.

Data on OSS use by small ISPs in Brazil

There is no clear data on the use of OSS by small ISPs in Brazil. As stated above in the justification, the terms "OSS," "free software," and "open source" do not even appear in the "ICT Providers" surveys coordinated and conducted by Cetic.br since 2011. There were no significant exact matches for either term in the bibliographic research and literature review. The preliminary interviews for the preparation of this detailed project, in particular the one with an owner and operator of an ISP in the metropolitan region of São Paulo who uses and advocates the use of OSS in providers, estimated a very high number of OSS users among small providers for economic reasons rather than knowledge of the characteristics of OSS. He also stated that there are no specific materials or booklets that compile and summarize the types of OSS use in providers, nor that suggest a specific stack of OSS for providers, and said he was very interested in receiving and contributing to and developing such material. Another preliminary interview with the owner and operator of an ISP in the city of Socorro, São Paulo, stated that there are some gaps in the OSS ecosystem for providers, especially when they grow in number of customers and with regard to Enterprise Resources Planning (ERP) software.

A community or small ISP is, in terms of software use, a small business that needs at least one server, and only a few ISP processes require specific software for this type of enterprise, such as the management of bandwidth delivered to customers, the status and operation of routers or cables, as in the case of a fiber optic network, or the software used in an OLT (Optical Line Terminal) in the case of a PON (Passive Optical Network). Most of the free software used in an ISP, such as ERP, is also used by other types of companies. ERP integrates customer relations, service purchase and complaint portals, billing, and service suspension in case of non-payment (called ticketing). There are software packages that perform more than one process simultaneously.

There are also “community networks” that rely on open-source software but do not operate as Internet Service Providers (ISPs) in the traditional sense (Beli, 2017;

Foditsch, 2017; Zanolli et al, 2018; Foditsch and Vo, 2025). These networks are typically organized and managed by local communities, cooperatives, or non-profit associations to provide connectivity and digital services in underserved areas. The most common practice is not to sell the internet, but only share the cost of the internet link among the beneficiary families. The community network movement is quite active and organized and is not only monitoring changes in legislation that also affect ISPs, but also discussing the use of OSS to expand connectivity and seeking to influence the design of public policies for digital inclusion and the execution of public resources aimed at universalizing telecommunications services.

4. Methodology

To the best of our knowledge this is the first specific study on the use of OSS in small ISPs in Brazil. For example, the most recent CETIC study on providers in Brazil, TIC -Provedores 2022, does not even mention "OSS," "free software," or "open source." Due to the specificity of this being a first systematic effort to produce knowledge about the interface between OSS and small ISPs, this research will be exploratory in nature and will combine qualitative and quantitative research methods. To prepare this report, a brief review of the literature on the subject was conducted, which proved to be quite scarce.

Due to its exploratory nature, the research first sought to understand, through at least five in-depth open interviews with key stakeholders: 1) their perception of the central object of the research, the use of OSS by small ISPs; 2) their perception of the adequacy and meaning of terms such as "small ISPs" and "community-focused ISPs" in the empirical reality of Brazil, as well as their perception of what would be an adequate number of users/customers to actually achieve community-focused ISPs; and 3) to understand the terminology and central concepts used in everyday life by owners and maintainers of small ISPs that centrally use OSS in their work processes.

As the research will have to fill gaps in empirical data, in addition to in-depth interviews, two different questionnaires were applied, one in person during an event held by a large entity in the sector, the Brazilian Internet Service Providers Congress, "ABRINT Global Congress", and the second will be administered online to as many small ISPs throughout Brazil as possible, based on the contacts gathered so far in the research. Based on questions from the questionnaire administered at ABRINT, an "in-depth interview script" was designed (See Appendix 1). Before administering the questionnaire at ABRINT, it was sent to two small providers that use OSS to be tested and

critiqued, and they suggested some changes to make it more understandable to other internet providers.

After this first round of conversations and interviews, based on the findings and terminology used, a first questionnaire was designed to be administered in person during the ABRINT Congress (see in Appendix 1 below). This round of questionnaires allowed us to better understand the regional differences in terminology and software actually used, some different understandings of the meaning of OSS, and to gather contacts for greater completion of the online questionnaire in the states of the federation. A total of 22 questionnaires were completed during the event. The analysis of these responses is in the "Preliminary Results" section below, and the tabulation of responses is at the end of this document in Appendix 3.

Based on the contacts and responses to the questionnaire administered at the ABRINT meeting, it was possible to develop a more refined online questionnaire, test the questionnaire with a small sample to verify the comprehensibility of the questions and terms, and then, with the help of key partners and their databases and contacts, distribute it so that it could be completed by as many small ISPs throughout Brazil as possible.

The set of questionnaires completed by small ISPs will be statistically analyzed and tabulated using statistical analysis software (such as RStudio, SPSS, or PSPP), providing more detailed empirical data on OSS use by ISPs and regional and ISP size differences, as well as the main difficulties and problems reported in this use. Based on the most widely used software, its cost will be surveyed and the costs between OSS and proprietary software will be compared, thus verifying the possibilities of reducing ISP costs through the adoption of OSS, as well as the installation or packaging of OSS that is sold.

A glossary of key terms and acronyms will be created to facilitate reading by diverse audiences who are not necessarily technical.

Various stakeholders working in this field in Brazil will be interviewed about their views on the establishment of ISPs, the use of OSS in community networks, and the experiences and best practices of ISPs using OSS in other countries.

Finally, we will discuss this analysis of the online questionnaire data with some key players in both the academic research field and the institutional field in the area (ABRINT and CETIC.br), as well as the communities of small ISPs that centrally use OSS to refine and validate the conclusions and research findings, and also to point out future avenues of research.

The study will employ interviews and questionnaires to explore potential hypotheses for the non-use of OSS, including limited awareness of its nature and functionalities, as well as the scarcity of training opportunities on its application among small providers. In light of the exploratory character of the research, variables related to social markers of difference, e.g. such as race, class, and gender, will not be incorporated at this stage, as their inclusion would require additional layers of analytical depth and complexity beyond the scope of the present design. Upon completion of this phase, the findings will inform the development of a training module on the use of OSS for small providers, to be delivered in collaboration with Ceptro.br / Nic.br.

The research conducted so far has been exploratory, reflecting the scarcity of data on the subject. To advance toward the creation of educational resources that can genuinely empower ISPs to adopt and promote OSS and open digital infrastructure—one of the central objectives of this process—it will be necessary to employ an additional methodological approach: action research, defined as “the study of a social situation with a view to improving the quality of action within it” (Elliott, 1991, as cited in Tripp, 2005). Small ISPs and other stakeholders engaged at the intersection of OSS and internet service provision possess a deeper understanding of the nuances of the issue: the software, its challenges, the operational contexts, and the broader ecosystem of ISPs. Ultimately, they are also the ones who will determine whether any educational resource developed through this research is used in practice.

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